

Tijaniyya Order/ الطريقة التيجانية

also known as "Aḥmad At-Tijānī"

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Entry tags: Sufi, Religious Group, Maghreb Religions, Islamic Traditions, Mysticism, Sufi Order

The Tijaniyya is a Sufi Tariqa (order). Its followers are present in many regions of the world, especially in North and Central Africa. Their number is estimated to be in the millions. Tijani (also transliterated as "Tidjani" following French orthography) practice is to gather every day in a meeting place, the zawiya, for collective Dhikr. They also gather every Friday for the Haylala of Friday, at which they repeat 1,200 times the word of God or the phrase: there is no god but God. They are distinguished by their strong love for the Prophet Muhammad, believers, and the general public, regardless of their religion.

Date Range: 1781 CE - 2022 CE

Region: North Africa and the Sahel

Region tags: Africa, Nigeria, Egypt, Sudan, North Africa, Tunisia, Sub-Saharan Africa

North Africa and the peoples of sub-Saharan Africa. A region that combines Arabs, Berbers and Africans. Muslims, Christians and Animists coexist

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: عامرة، الشاسي، الخطاب الصوفي وإشكالاته التواصلية: الطريقة التيجانية أمودجا، جامعة محمد خيضر، بسكرة، 2015:

– Source 2: Trimmingham, J. Spencer, The Sufi Orders in Islam, Oxford University Press, 1971.

– Source 3: Schmitz, Jean, "Autour d'al-Hājj Umar Taal Guerre sainte et Tijaniyya en Afrique de l'Ouest", in Cahiers d'Etudes africaines, 100, XXV-4, 1985, pp 555-565.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

– Source 1: Wright, Zachary Valentine, Realising Islam The Tijaniyya in North Africa and the Eighteenth-Century Muslim World, the University of North Carolina Press, 2020

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

– Source 2: Melliti, Imed, La zawiya en tant que foyer de socialité le cas des tijaniyya de Tunis, thèse encadré par Michel Maffesoli, Université Paris V René Descartes sciences humaines - Sorbonne, Paris, 1993.

– Source 3: Ben Abdallah, Abdelaziz, La Tijania une voie spirituelle et sociale, Al Quobba Zarqua, Marrakech, 1999

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL:

<https://www.aljazeera.net/news/politics/2020/3/9/%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B7%D8%B1%D9%8A%D9%82%D8%A9-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AA%D9%8A%D8%AC%D8%A7%D9%86%D9%8A%D8%A9-%D8%B9%D9%84%D9%8A-%D8%A8%D9%84%D8%B9%D8%B1%D8%A7%D8%A8%D9%8A-%D8%AA%D8%B4%D8%A7%D8%AF>

– Source 2 URL: <https://tidjaniya.com/fr/tidjaniya-com-site-officiel-de-la-tariqa-tidjaniya/>

– Source 2 Description: الموقع الرسمي للطريقة التيجانية، وهو لا يعني عن المواقع الأخرى الهامة

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.library-skiredj.com/>

– Source 3 Description: موقع فيه أهم كتب الشيخ سكيرج وهو من الأعلام الكبار للطريقة التيجانية

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://theses.univ-oran1.dz/document/62201708t.pdf>

– Source 1 Description: لكتاب باللغة العربية وهو أطروحة دكتوراه في جامعة وهران بالجزائر أهم فصوله: انتشار الطريقة التيجانية في شمال إفريقيا وغرب إفريقيا (ص 64-78): (موقف الطريقة من قضية التحديد في شمال وغرب إفريقيا ص 117-129).

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Umar-Tal#ref101051> (accessed on September 26 2022)

–Source 2 Description: حول شخصيّة عمر الفوني وأهمّيّتها

–Source 3 URL: <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/downArticle/295/1/3/17272>

–Source 3 Description: A university study on Sheikh Ahmad Tijani and the emergence of Sufi thought.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Berrada, Sidi Ali Harazem, Extraits de l'ouvrage Jawahir Al-Maani (Perles des Indications et Compréhensions), tr. Abdelaziz Benabdellah.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Notes: The change here does not affect the letters or the meanings, but rather is related to the good output or the reprinting of the texts with some explanation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: They are usually religious scholars who can explain what is stated in those books. But they do not have a monopoly on understanding and interpretation

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The Holy Quran, Hadith books, Biography books, Maliki jurisprudence

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: If we mean by religion Islam, the religious groups connected to it are very numerous. In the area we are studying, we find many varied Sufi Turuq. Brenner, Louis, *West African Sufi the Heritage and Spiritual Search of Cerno Bokar Saalif Taal*, University of California Pr, Berkeley and Los Angeles, p 39.

Reference: Brenner, Louis. *West African Sufi the Heritage and Spiritual Search of Cerno Bokar Saalif Taal*. Berkeley and Los Angeles: University of California Press, 1984. <https://books.google.tn/books?id=bCkogLL2LJwC&pg=PA39&dq=sufi+orders+in+west+africa&hl=fr&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEwi4saKi08P6AhUPHuwKHV8AkMQ6AF6BAGHEAI#v=onepage!>

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Especially between the Tijani Sufi Tariqa and the Qadiriya Sufi Tariqa

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Colonialism was the cause of the conflict between the Sufi Turuq (plural of Tariqa), although its principles reject religious conflict

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: The violent conflict between extremists (Wahhabis) and other Muslims, and between Muslims in general and Christians Jean Louis Triaud mentioned: "La Tidjaniya est exposée, plus que toute autre confrérie, aux dénonciations périodiques des secteurs fondamentalistes de l'islam africain, qui voient en elle une déviation de l'orthodoxie sunnite, ce qu'elle réfute vigoureusement, en nuancant d'ailleurs certaines de ses affirmations les plus audacieuses." <https://www.cairn.info/revue-politique-etrangere-2010-4-page-831.htm>

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: The violent conflict in general is between Muslims and extremists, but especially between the Sufi Turuq, including the Tijaniyyah, and the terrorists

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: it is the same architecture as the Mosques

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Notes: The mosque for Muslims is a private building and is not linked to other buildings. The place of worship for Muslims in general, or for the tijani's dhikr, has no characteristics related to its size, length and height...

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Notes: Aïn Madhi in Al-Aghwat Algeria

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 3000000000

Notes: Today, there would be more than 300 million followers in the world to claim Ahmed Al Tijani and all wish to meditate on his tomb, in Fez. <https://www.jeuneafrique.com/mag/235261/culture/fes-la-tijane/#:~:text=Aujourd%27hui%2C%20ils%20seraient%20plus,se%20revendique%20capitale%20des%20tijanes.>

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: Affiliation to the order is achieved by agreement on the conditions that the Sheikh presents to the disciple and the covenant not to abandon the litanies. see Holy people of the world, p 858

Reference: Jestice, Phyllis G., ed. Holy People of the World : A Cross-cultural Encyclopedia. Edited by Phyllis G. Jestice. Santa Barbara, California: ABC-CLIO, Inc., n.d..

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: Belonging to the Tijani Tariqa is not hereditary, but often the sons of the founder of the Tijani Tariqa become Tijanies

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: To be Tijani is a personal choice and is not binding

Reference: العرافي, سيدي إدريس. "مزايما الطريقة التجانية". موقع الطريقة التجانية. July 4, 2020. <https://www.tidjania.ma/2020/07/04/%D9%85%D8%B2%D8%A7%D9%8A%D8%A7-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B7%D8%B1%D9%8A%D9%82%D8%A9-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AA%D8%AC%D8%A7%D9%86%D9%8A%D8%A9-2/>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Belonging to the Tidjani Tariqa is a personal choice, and nothing obliges a Muslim to be a Tijani

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Tombs:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Cemeteries:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Temples:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Altars:
– Field doesn't know
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Devotional markers:
– I don't know
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: As long as affiliation to the Tariqa is based on the free will, the Tijanias do not preach their Sufi way
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Mostly, the Tijanias do not receive official aid from the state, unlike some other Turuq such as

Qadiriyyah (in Tunisia during the time of President Zine El Abidine Ben Ali). The political support from the state to the Tijaniya tariqa differs from one state to another in the studied region.

Reference: - عبد الحفيظ حمي. "الطريقة التجانية في الجزائر وموقف السلطة العثمانية منها من خلال المصادر المحلية 1196 هـ (1782-1826م)". *أفاق فكرية* 7 (May 21, 2019). <https://www.asjp.cerist.dz/en/downArticle/596/7/1/87383>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

Notes: There are no priests in the Tariqa Tijania. there is no official function in the Tariqa Tijania.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: There is no structural relationship between the Tijaniya Tariqa and the state. The Regimes of the studied region do not require that the president of the state has to be a Sufi or belong to a Sufi Tariqa

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Tijania Tariqa doesn't care about that

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Is iconography present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: We do not find this in the area we are studying

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: There is no administrative or political supervision, but rather the concern and love of the general caliph

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
– Optional (rare)

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: If we mean by religion Islam, the religious groups connected to it are very numerous. In the area we are studying, we find many varied Sufi Turuq. Brenner, Louis, *West African Sufi the Heritage and Spiritual Search of Cerno Bokar Saalif Taal*, University of California Pr, Berkeley and Los Angeles, p 39.

Reference: Brenner, Louis. *West African Sufi the Heritage and Spiritual Search of Cerno Bokar Saalif Taal*. Berkeley and Los Angeles: University of California Press, 1984. <https://books.google.tn/books?id=bCxogLL2LJwC&pg=PA39&dq=sufi+orders+in+west+africa&hl=fr&sa=X&ved=2ahUKewi4saKi08P6AhUPHuwKHVa8AkMQ6AF6BAGHEAI#v=onepag>

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:
– Yes

Notes: Especially between the Tijani Sufi Tariqa and the Qadiriya Sufi Tariqa

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:
– Yes

Notes: Colonialism was the cause of the conflict between the Sufi Turuq (plural of Tariqa), although its principles reject religious conflict

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):
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Notes: The violent conflict between extremists (Wahhabis) and other Muslims, and between Muslims in general and Christians Jean Louis Triaud mentioned: "La Tidjaniya est exposée, plus que toute autre confrérie, aux dénonciations périodiques des secteurs fondamentalistes de l'islam africain, qui voient en elle une déviation de l'orthodoxie sunnite, ce qu'elle réfute vigoureusement, en nuançant d'ailleurs certaines de ses affirmations les plus audacieuses." <https://www.cairn.info/revue-politique-etrangere-2010-4-page-831.htm>

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):
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Notes: The violent conflict in general is between Muslims and extremists, but especially between the Sufi Turuq, including the Tijaniyyah, and the terrorists

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: Affiliation to the order is achieved by agreement on the conditions that the Sheikh presents to the disciple and the covenant not to abandon the litanies. see Holy people of the world, p 858

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Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: Belonging to the Tijani Tariqa is not hereditary, but often the sons of the founder of the Tijani Tariqa become Tijanies

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Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

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Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

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Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

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Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Assigned by gender:

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Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

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Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Belonging to the Tidjani Tariqa is a personal choice, and nothing obliges a Muslim to be a Tijani

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: As long as affiliation to the Tariqa is based on the free will, the tijanies do not preach their Sufi way

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— Yes

Notes: Mostly, the Tijanias do not receive official aid from the state, unlike some other Turuq such as Qadiriyyah (in Tunisia during the time of President Zine El Abidine Ben Ali). The political support from the state to the Tijaniya tariqa differs from one state to another in the studied region.

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Specific to this answer:

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Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

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Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

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Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

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Notes: The Tijania Tariqa doesn't care about that

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

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Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Notes: We do not find this in the area we are studying

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 3000000000

Notes: Today, there would be more than 300 million followers in the world to claim Ahmed Al Tijani and all wish to meditate on his tomb, in Fez. <https://www.jeuneafrique.com/mag/235261/culture/fes-la-tijane/#:~:text=Aujourd%27hui%2C%20ils%20seraient%20plus,se%20revendique%20capitale%20des%20tijanes.>

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

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Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

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Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

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↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

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↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Berrada, Sidi Ali Harazem, Extraits de l'ouvrage Jawahir Al-Maani (Perles des Indications et Compréhensions), tr. Abdelaziz Benabdellah.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Notes: The change here does not affect the letters or the meanings, but rather is related to the good output or the reprinting of the texts with some explanation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: They are usually religious scholars who can explain what is stated in those books. But they do not have a monopoly on understanding and interpretation

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The Holy Quran, Hadith books, Biography books, Maliki jurisprudence

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

— Yes

Notes: it is the same architecture as the Mosques

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

— I don't know

Notes: The mosque for Muslims is a private building and is not linked to other buildings. The place of worship for Muslims in general, or for the tijani's dhikr , has no characteristics related to its size, length and height...

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

— I don't know

Notes: Ain Madhi in Al-Aghwat Algeria

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Tombs:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Cemeteries:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Temples:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Altars:

— Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Devotional markers:

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:
— No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Is iconography present:
— No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:
— Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:
"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...
— No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Are pilgrimages present:
— Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
— Optional (rare)

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

— Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:
— Yes

Notes: The soul (and not the spirit) in the perception of Tijanis has characteristics that transcend the body. This is the same conception that other Muslims, Christians and Jews have...

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:
— Yes

Notes: The Soul (not the spirit) is from God, it's in some way the breath of God Sidi Ahmed Tijani disait: "Il y a l'amour général émanant d'Allah le Très Haut et Glorieux, qui concerne tout l'univers, y compris les mécréants inclus dans cet amour, eu égard à Son Verbe Sacré : « ...J'ai aimé être connu, et J'ai donné l'existence à des créatures, puis Je Me suis fait connaître à elles, c'est par Moi qu'elles M'ont connu... » ; N'imagine donc pas qu'une créature quelconque a été négligée dans cette connaissance ; toutes les âmes ainsi dotées d'une pleine connaissance d'Allah le Très Haut, ont été frappées d'ignorance par leur insertion dans le corps... ; on peut rétorquer en se

demandant pourquoi leurs corps étaient taxés d'ignorance d'Allah, alors qu'ils sont soumis au verdict « ...J'ai aimé être connu ... » ; la réponse est qu'en fait les corps des mécréants ne comportent guère une quelconque ignorance d'Allah le Très Haut, mais en ont seulement une conception particulière, différente de celle de l'âme, par laquelle ils (les corps) deviennent conscients d'Allah , Auquel ils se prosternent , proclamant Sa Gloire, sans nulle connaissance de l'association à Allah, qui a frappé leur âme ... (pp 37-38)

Reference: Harazem Berrada, Sidi Ali. Extrait De L'ouvrage Jawahir Al Maani: (perles Des Indications Et Compréhensions) Recueilli Auprès Du Cheikh Sidi Ahmed Tijani, n.d.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: الروح (وهي غير النفس) خالدة لأن جوهريها ليس من الأرض بل من الله

Notes: "Questionné sur le verset : « Lorsque Je lui aurai donné sa forme et insufflé en lui de Mon Esprit, prosternerez-vous à Lui ! » (sourate al-hijr v.23), - il répondit : l'insufflation veut dire l'intégration de l'âme dans le corps, et l'appellation est en rapport avec le Souffle Divin , tandis que l'assignation de l'acte par Allah l'Impartial à Lui-même , signifie Création et Spécification ... ainsi que la transcendance de Son degré par rapport à tous ceux autres que Lui parmi Ses créatures ; c'est là le sens de l'attachement relatif à Son Esprit ; l'âme évoquée ici est l'âme animale géant les corps et animateur de la vie... , faisant émerger l'image de la vie en elle , puis en son sein l'âme divine sacrée (qodsi) , grâce à laquelle l'âme humaine a acquis ascendance et suprématie sur tous les degrés du créé ... ; cette âme animale était en vie éternelle du fait de l'âme sacrée (qodsi) , car l'âme n'insère en-elle que ce qui a été accordé au corps : vie, sens, et mobilité , ainsi que ce qu'elle englobe comme exigences et conséquences , dont l'âme animale est dépourvue ... ;tandis que l'âme sacrée a doté l'âme animale de la plénitude du Savoir de l'Instance Divine, comme elle lui a accordé également la connaissance de ce qu'on attend d'elle, ainsi que le mobile de sa création ... ; et de ce fait l'âme animale est devenue le "khalife" d'Allah sur tout l'univers. l'âme animale, ajoute Sidna Ech-Cheikh, tient sa vie de cette insufflation (sourate al-hijr v.23), parce que sans elle serait similaire aux autres animaux, n'ayant nullement un surcroît quelconque de suprématie ou autre; l'âme qodsi est en fait une sublime lumière émanant de l'Instance de l'Impartial , portant en elle une plénitude infinie de lumières, secrets et sciences ; et quand l'âme qodsi s'insère dans l'âme animale, elle lui octroie tous les degrés de transcendance précités , entre autres son khilafa ; quand tu auras bien conçu et analysé ce fait, tu sauras la portée du degré de l'homme ...distinguant l'Elu accompli de celui qui ne l'est pas , et le mort du vivant ..." (Jawahir pp57-58)

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– No

Notes: Unseen beings watch people but do not interfere in their actions

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: according to Tijanians making major sins may lead to a great punishment before death, this may be due to unseen beings

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Food:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: To protect "good" believers, even from themselves

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 – I don't know
 Specific to this answer:
 Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 – I don't know
 Specific to this answer:
 Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 – Yes
 Specific to this answer:
 Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 – I don't know
 Specific to this answer:
 Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 – Yes
 Specific to this answer:
 Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 – Yes
 Specific to this answer:
 Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 – I don't know
 Specific to this answer:
 Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 – I don't know
 Specific to this answer:
 Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 – I don't know
 Specific to this answer:
 Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 – Yes [specify]: حماية أهل الطريقة من الظلم ومن الكائنات الشريرة الخفية
 Notes: I understand the phrase "attention" in the meaning of follow-up and care, not in the meaning of direct intervention in the lives of believers, except in rare cases.
 Specific to this answer:
 Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: It is the social ethics in Islam

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: The same believe as Muslims

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Alive, identified:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Coming on specified date:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Notes: He is not a political figure in common sense, but he performs a political function of bringing justice

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: التصور حول المسيح هو التصور العام الذي يوجد عند المسلمين.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme God among the Tijanis, like all Muslims, and like Christians and Jews, is the One God

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: God is everywhere not only in the sky

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: God is the Lord of the living and the dead

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: In some historical Islamic religious groups, we find that the ruler is the shadow of God on earth. And what Al-Tijanis believe is close to this. They look to the ruler with great respect and consider that God has assigned him to do what he is doing.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Notes: هو ظل الله في الأرض. وهو خليفته ولكنه ليس معصوماً من الخطأ مثل الرسل والأنبياء يقول سيدي أحمد التيجاني في جواهر المعاني: "وسألته رضي الله عنه عن معنى قوله صلى الله عليه وسلم في الحديث: «ينزل ربنا كل ليلة إلى سماء الدنيا...» الخ الحديث. فأجاب رضي الله عنه بقوله: «علم أنّ للحق سبحانه وتعالى في مرتبة ذاته نسبتين: نسبة الكثرة، وهذه المرتبة بعيدة عن التغير بالزمان والمكان والنسب والإضافات والجهات والتوجهات، لا تقبل شيئاً من هذه النسب لا ظاهراً ولا باطناً ولا حقيقة ولا مجازاً، والنسبة الثانية: نسبة التنزل، إنّها بالنبأ وإثماً بالرحمة والفضل، وإثماً بالغضب والبطش، وإثماً بالاشتراك. فأثماً نسبة النبأ فهو مثل قوله صلى الله عليه وسلم: «السلطان ظلّ الله في الأرض» ومعناه ينوب عن الله سبحانه وتعالى بإيقاع الخير والنشر لإصلاح الأرض، كلّ بما يختص به من أهله، وكقوله سبحانه وتعالى: / إني جاعل في الأرض خليفة / فهذا تنزل النبأ.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: God promised the believers, the rulers and others, that they would be rewarded according to their actions. Rulers are closer to God than others

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: This knowledge generated many theological issues, the most important of which is the issue of fate and destiny. Al-Tijanis deeply believe in predestination and the ability of man to act freely at the same time. يقول الشيخ الأحسن البعقلي في كتابه "الشرب الصافي" في الجزء الثاني: "فاختيار الله تخصيص الإرادة القدرة بأحد طرفي الممكن واختيار العبد قصد الفعل ليفعله لياشتره وهو النية بمعنى القصد وهو الكسب الذي علقته به الأحكام الشرعية فإذا ذبح مثلا بلا نية جافت ونية طابت فالفرق بين فعلين صادرين من العبد فإن كان من قصد له فكس وإن كان عن اضطرار كالارتعاش فحبر فمن نسب الفعل بالقوة للعبد اعتزل ويسمى قدريا ومن نفى الفعل بطريق الكسب على وجه الاختيار بالقصد نحو الفعل ليفعله فهو جبري فأدى بآزمه إلى سقوط التكليف"

Reference: الأحسن، البعقلي. الشرب الصافي من الكرم الوافي على جواهر المعاني. Edited by الصائغ بن سالم محمّد. Vol. 2. المطبعة العربية بدمشق. الدار البيضاء المغرب: n.d.. <https://zaouiatijania.ovh/livre/ChorbSafi02.pdf>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ In trance possession:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Through divination practices:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Yes

Notes: Ces spécialistes sont les prophètes, et il sont choisis par Dieu

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Only through monarch
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Other form of communication with living:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: Sidi Omar Fouti said: "And if you know all of what we have mentioned, you will know that the presence of the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, and with him the four Caliphs, may God Almighty be pleased with them with their bodies and souls, when reciting the Jawharat Kamal, when reciting any Dhikr, and at any assembly or place he wanted," (The End of the chapter 31)

Reference: Omar, Fouti, رماح حزب الرحيم على نخور حزب الرحيم. Vol. 1. دار الكتب العلمية، 2019. <http://www.al-ilmiyah.com/details?id=978-2-7451-6253-3>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ In dreams:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ In trance possession:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ Through divination processes:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ Only through specialists:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ Only through monarch:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ **Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
 - ↳ **Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:**
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
 - ↳ **Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:**
 - I don't know
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
 - ↳ **Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:**
 - I don't know
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
 - ↳ **Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:**
 - I don't know
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
 - ↳ **Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
 - ↳ **Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
 - ↳ **Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
 - ↳ **Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):**
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
 - ↳ **Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):**
 - I don't know
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
 - ↳ **Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Other organization for pantheon:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Belief in afterlife:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:
– Yes [specify]: في بعض الأحيان للميت القدرة على مراقبة الأحياء وزيارتهم
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:
– No
Notes: convention veut dire accord entre deux ou plusieurs personnes. alors que morale est l'ensemble des règles qui doivent diriger l'activité libre de l'homme. En Islam et dans la Tariqa Tijaniya il n'y a pas de conventions internes qui peuvent être contradictoires avec les règles qui gèrent la vie commune de la société.
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: Yes in most cases, but the causes may not be known

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The matter is a little complicated, the punishment may not be the result of sins, but rather the result of laziness or disregard for the covenant that the individual imposed on himself. It is to be loyal to God

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Any Muslim becomes *tijany* when he agrees to the terms of entering the *Tariqa*. If he betrays his covenant, he will be punished.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The punishment after death according to Al-Tijani is the well-known punishment in Islam and Judaism

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Al-Tijani is afraid of God's wrath and that he will die, and God is not satisfied

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 – No
 Specific to this answer:
 Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 – Yes
 Specific to this answer:
 Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 – No
 Specific to this answer:
 Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 – No
 Specific to this answer:
 Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 – No
 Specific to this answer:
 Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 – Yes
 Notes: Sickness may be a blessing, not a punishment, in order to cleanse the guilty of his sins
 Specific to this answer:
 Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 – Yes
 Specific to this answer:
 Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 – Yes
 Specific to this answer:
 Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Other [specify]
 – Yes
 Notes: In Islam in general, punishment is not always torture, but rather it may be a trial of wealth and beauty
 Specific to this answer:
 Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: يمكن أن يكون الميت حاضرا في الحياة العائمة ولكنها ليست عودة إلى الحياة مثلما نجد ذلك عند من يقولون بالتناسخ

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

- ↳ **Courage (in battle):**
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ **Courage (generic):**
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ **Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:**
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ **Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:**
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ **Generosity / charity:**
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ **Selflessness / selfless giving:**
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ **Righteousness / moral rectitude:**
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ **Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:**
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ **Respectfulness / courtesy:**
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ **Familial obedience / filial piety:**
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ **Fidelity / loyalty:**
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa
- ↳ **Cooperation:**
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Moderation / frugality:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Strength (physical):
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Power / status / nobility:
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Humility / modesty:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Wisdom / understanding:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Discernment / intelligence:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
– I don't know
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The soul (and not the spirit) in the perception of Tijanis has characteristics that transcend the body. This is the same conception that other Muslims, Christians and Jews have...

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: The Soul (not the spirit) is from God, it's in some way the breath of God Sidi Ahmed Tijani disait: "Il y a l'amour général émanant d'Allah le Très Haut et Glorieux, qui concerne tout l'univers, y compris les mécréants inclus dans cet amour, eu égard à Son Verbe Sacré : « ...J'ai aimé être connu, et J'ai donné l'existence à des créatures, puis Je Me suis fait connaître à elles, c'est par Moi qu'elles M'ont connu... » ; N'imagine donc pas qu'une créature quelconque a été négligée dans cette connaissance ; toutes les âmes ainsi dotées d'une pleine connaissance d'Allah le Très Haut, ont été frappées d'ignorance par leur insertion dans le corps... ; on peut rétorquer en se demandant pourquoi leurs corps étaient taxés d'ignorance d'Allah, alors qu'ils sont soumis au verdict « ...J'ai aimé être connu ... » ; la réponse est qu'en fait les corps des mécréants ne comporte guère une quelconque ignorance d'Allah le Très Haut, mais en ont seulement une conception particulière, différente de celle de l'âme, par laquelle ils (les corps) deviennent conscients d'Allah , Auquel ils se prosternent , proclamant Sa Cloire, sans nulle connaissance de l'association à Allah, qui a frappé leur âme ... (pp 37-38)

Reference: Harazem Berrada, Sidi Ali. Extrait De L'ouvrage Jawahir Al Maani: (perles Des Indications Et Compréhensions) Recueilli Auprès Du Cheikh Sidi Ahmed Tijani, n.d..

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: الروح (وهي غير النفس) خالدة لأن جوهرها ليس من الأرض بل من الله

Notes: "Questionné sur le verset : « Lorsque Je lui aurai donné sa forme et insufflé en lui de Mon Esprit, prosternerez-vous à lui ! » (sourate al-hijr v.23), - il répondit : l'insufflation veut dire l'intégration de l'âme dans le corps, et l'appellation est en rapport avec le Souffle Divin , tandis que l'assignation de l'acte par Allah l'Impartial à Lui-même , signifie Création et Spécification ... ainsi que la transcendance de Son degré par rapport à tous ceux autres que Lui parmi Ses créatures ; c'est là le sens de l'attachement relatif à Son Esprit ; l'âme évoquée ici est l'âme animal gérant les corps et animateur de la vie... , faisant émerger l'image de la vie en elle , puis en son sein l'âme divine sacrée (qodsi) , grâce à laquelle l'âme humaine a acquis ascendance et suprématie sur tous les degrés du créé ... ; cette âme animale était en vie éternelle du fait de l'âme sacrée (qodsi) , car l'âme n'insère en-elle que ce qui a été accordé au corps : vie, sens, et mobilité , ainsi que ce qu'elle englobe comme exigences et conséquences , dont l'âme animale est dépourvue ... ; tandis que l'âme sacrée a doté l'âme animale de la plénitude du Savoir de l'Instance Divine, comme elle lui a accordé également la connaissance de ce qu'on attend d'elle, ainsi que le mobile de sa création ... ; et de ce fait l'âme animale est devenue le "khalife" d'Allah sur tout l'univers. l'âme animale, ajoute Sidna Ech-Cheikh, tient sa vie de cette insufflation (sourate al-hijr v.23), parce que sans elle serait similaire aux autres animaux, n'ayant nullement un surcroît quelconque de suprématie ou autre; l'âme qodsi est en fait une sublime lumière émanant de l'Instance de l'Impartial , portant en elle une plénitude infinie de lumières, secrets et sciences ; et quand l'âme qodsi s'insère dans l'âme animale, elle lui octroie tous les degrés de transcendance précités , entre autres son khilafa ; quand tu auras bien conçu et analysé ce fait, tu sauras la portée du degré de l'homme ...distinguant l'Elu accompli de celui qui ne l'est pas , et le mort du vivant ..." (Jawahir pp57-58)

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:
– Yes [specify]: في بعض الأحيان للميت القدرة على مراقبة الأحياء وزيارتهم

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: يمكن أن يكون الميت حاضرا في الحياة العاقبة ولكنها ليست عودة إلى الحياة مثلما نجد ذلك عند من يقولون بالتناسخ.

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ As cenotaphs:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ In cemetery:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Family tomb-crypt:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):
– No
Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme God among the Tijanis, like all Muslims, and like Christians and Jews, is the One God

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: God is everywhere not only in the sky

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: God is the Lord of the living and the dead

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: In some historical Islamic religious groups, we find that the ruler is the shadow of God on earth. And what Al-Tijanis believe is close to this. They look to the ruler with great respect and consider that God has assigned him to do what he is doing.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Notes: هو ظل الله في الأرض. وهو خليفته ولكنه ليس معصوماً من الخطأ مثل الرسل والأنبياء يقول سيدي أحمد التجاني في جواهر المعاني: "وسألته رضي الله عنه عن معنى قوله صلى الله عليه وسلم في الحديث: «ينزل ربنا كل ليلة كل ليلة إلى سماء الدنيا ...» إلخ الحديث. فأجاب رضي الله عنه بقوله: «إعلم أنّ للحق سبحانه وتعالى في مرتبة ذاته نسبتين: نسبة الكثرة، وهذه المرتبة بعيدة عن التغير بالزمان والمكان والنسب والإضافات والجهات والتوجهات، لا تقبل شيئاً من هذه النسب لا ظاهراً ولا باطناً ولا حقيقة ولا مجازاً، والنسبة الثانية: نسبة التنزل، إما بالنبية وإما بالرحمة والفضل، وإما بالعصب والبطش، وإما بالاشترار. فأما نسبة النبوة فهو مثل قوله صلى الله عليه وسلم: «السلطان ظلُّ الله في الأرض» ومعناه ينوب عن الله سبحانه وتعالى بإيقاع الخير والنشر لإصلاح الأرض، كلُّ بما يختصُّ به من أهله، وبقوله سبحانه وتعالى: /إِنِّي جَاعِلٌ فِي الْأَرْضِ خَلِيفَةً / فهذا نزل النبوة.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
– Yes [specify]: God promised the believers, the rulers and others, that they would be rewarded according to their actions. Rulers are closer to God than others

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: This knowledge generated many theological issues, the most important of which is the issue of fate and destiny. Al-Tijanis deeply believe in predestination and the ability of man to act freely at the same time. يقول الشيخ الأحسن البعقلي في كتابه "الشرب الصافي" في الجزء الثاني: "فاختيار الله تخصيص الإرادة القدرة باحد طرفي الممكن واختيار العبد قصد الفعل ليفعله لياشهره وهو النية بمعنى القصد وهو الكسب الذي علقته به الاحكام الشرعية فإذا دبح مثلا بلا نية جافت ونية طابت فالفرق بين فعلين صادرين من العبد فان كان من قصد له فكس وإن كان عن اضطرار كالارتعاش فغير فمن نسب الفعل بالقوة للعبد اعتزل وسمى قدريا ومن نفى الفعل بطريق الكسب على وجه الاختيار بالقصد نحو "الفعل ليفعله فهو جبري فأدى بلازمه الى سقوط التكليف"

Reference: الأحسن، البعقلي. الشرب الصافي من الكرم الوافي على جواهر المعاني. Edited by الصانع بن سالم محمّد. Vol. 2. المطبعة العربية بدار غلف 2. n.d. <https://zaouiatijania.ovh/livre/ChorbSafi02.pdf>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ In trance possession:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Ces spécialistes sont les prophètes, et il sont choisis par Dieu
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - Yes

Notes: Sidi Omar Fouti said: "And if you know all of what we have mentioned, you will know that the presence of the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, and with him the four Caliphs, may God Almighty be pleased with them with their bodies and souls, when reciting the Jawharat Kamal, when reciting any Dhikr, and at any assembly or place he wanted," (The End of the chapter 31)

Reference: Omar, Fouti, رماح حزب الرحيم على نحو حزب الرحيم, Vol. 1. دار الكتب العلمية, 2019. <http://www.al-ilmiyah.com/details?id=978-2-7451-6253-3>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ In trance possession:
 - I don't know
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Through divination processes:
 - I don't know
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Only through specialists:
 - I don't know
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - I don't know
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - I don't know
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - I don't know
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– No

Notes: Unseen beings watch people but do not interfere in their actions

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: according to Tijanies making major sins may lead to a great punishment before death, this may be due to unseen beings

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Food:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: To protect "good" believers, even from themselves

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: حماية أهل الطريقة من الظلم ومن الكائنات الشريرة الخفية

Notes: I understand the phrase "attention" in the meaning of follow-up and care, not in the meaning of direct intervention in the lives of believers, except in rare cases.

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Done only by high god:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
– Yes

Notes: Yes in most cases, but the causes may not be known

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]
– Yes

Notes: The matter is a little complicated, the punishment may not be the result of sins, but rather the result of laziness or disregard for the covenant that the individual imposed on himself. It is to be loyal to God

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Done to enforce group norms:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Done randomly:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Other [specify]
– Yes

Notes: Any Muslim becomes tijany when he agrees to the terms of entering the Tariqa. If he betrays his covenant, he will be punished.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Yes
 - Notes: The punishment after death according to Al-Tijani is the well-known punishment in Islam and Judaism
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Al-Tijani is afraid of God's wrath and that he will die, and God is not satisfied
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - No
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: Sickness may be a blessing, not a punishment, in order to cleanse the guilty of his sins

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: In Islam in general, punishment is not always torture, but rather it may be a trial of wealth and beauty

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: The same believe as Muslims

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Alive, identified:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Coming on specified date:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Coming has already passed:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:
– Yes

Notes: He is not a political figure in common sense, but he performs a political function of bringing justice

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: التصور حول المسيح هو التصور العام الذي يوجد عند المسلمين.

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: It is the social ethics in Islam

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: convention veut dire accord entre deux ou plusieurs personnes. alors que morale est l'ensemble des règles qui doivent diriger l'activité libre de l'homme. En Islam et dans la Tariqa Tijaniya il n'y a pas de conventions internes qui peuvent être contradictoires avec les règles qui gèrent la vie commune de la société.

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Courage (in battle):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Courage (generic):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Generosity / charity:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - I don't know
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
 - Specific to this answer:
 - Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes

- Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
– I don't know
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: هو صوم المسلمين المعلوم

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: الصلوات اليومية العادية عند المسلمين واجتماع يومي للوظيفة

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
— No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
— No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:
E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.
— No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:
— No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):
— No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):
— No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require castration:
— No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:
— Yes

Notes: هو صوم المسلمين المعلوم

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):
— No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:
— No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: الصلوات اليومية العادية عند المسلمين واجتماع يومي للوظيفة

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Sufi Order or Sufi Tariqa

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes
Notes: state military force

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes
Notes: By the state

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Trading; public employment
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes
Notes: The state is responsible for this. Tijani are citizens and they enjoy these services

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes
Notes: If we mean by the tax collector the state

Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes
Notes: By the state
Specific to this answer:
Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Notes: There is no specific language

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

— Yes

Notes: like the bureaucracy of all state institutions

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: L'arabe, le français, l'anglais.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: c'est l'état qui fournit

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: state institutions

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The state is responsible for this. Tijani are citizens and they enjoy these services

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Subsaharan Africa

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Sufi Order or Sufi Tariqa

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: like the bureaucracy of all state institutions

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The state is responsible for this. Tijani are citizens and they enjoy these services

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: c'est l'état qui fournit

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: The state is responsible for this. Tijani are citizens and they enjoy these services

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: If we mean by the tax collector the state

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: **state institutions**

Specific to this answer:

Region: **North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa**

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa**

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa**

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa**

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa**

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa**

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: **North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa**

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa**

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: **North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa**

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: **state military force**

Specific to this answer:

Region: **North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa**

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: **North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa**

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: There is no specific language

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: L'arabe, le français, l'anglais.

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: By the state

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: By the state

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Trading; public employment

Specific to this answer:

Region: North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa

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